

Systems Biology of Alzheimer's Disease: Biophysics and Computational Modelling

Prof. Don Kulasiri

Lincoln University, Centre for Advanced Computational Solutions
(C-fACS), Lincoln, Christ-church, NEW ZEALAND

Email: don.kulasiri@lincoln.ac.nz

Abstract:

During the past few decades, systems biology approach to understand the intracellular bio-chemical pathway interactions using computational biophysical models has become increasingly valuable in neuroscience, especially to study the temporal and spatial complexities in single cell dynamics. Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a devastating, incurable neuro-degenerative disease involving dysregulation of intracellular Ca^{2+} signalling which has been observed to be an early event prior to the presence of clinical symptoms of AD contributing to its pathogenesis. AD also is a result of breakdown of healthy operational regimes of synaptic plasticity, which reflects the brain's ability to be flexible in transmitting a large repertoire of signals across synapses, the connections between neurons. In this speech, we will briefly discuss the biophysical models we have developed related to synaptic plasticity based on the associated biochemical pathways. First, we overview a model related to bidirectional modulations of the postsynaptic response following a synaptic transmission in a postsynaptic cell. Within the system of pathways, a synaptic protein, Ca^{2+} /Calmodulin dependent protein kinase II (CaMKII), plays a major role in the memory formation and impairment, and it is often called "the memory molecule." Secondly, we will give an overview of a model of the formation of CaMKII-NMDAR complex with the full state transitions of CaMKII, including the autophosphorylation.

Further, we will briefly overview the presynaptic short-term plasticity model which is developed to understand the neurotransmitter dynamics. Synaptotagmin 7 (Syt7), a presynaptic calcium sensor, has a significant role in the facilitation, a form of short-term plasticity. The functional importance of short-term plasticity is not well understood but its dysfunction plays a role in AD. In this study, we attempt to investigate the potential functional relationship between the short-term plasticity and postsynaptic response.

Lastly, we explain a computational model of a CA1 pyramidal dendritic spine, integrating essential components and reactions related to NMDAR-mediated Ca^{2+} response in the dendritic spine. Using this model, computational experiments are conducted to mimic major alterations under AD conditions; and the alterations in glutamate availability, as well as NMDAR availability and activity, are studied individually and globally.

Keywords:

Alzheimer's disease; synaptic plasticity; bio-physics; computational models; memory; Ca^{2+} dysregulation.

Biography :

Prof. Don Kulasiri obtained the BSc Eng (honours) at University of Peradeniya (1980) Sri Lanka and MS and PhD in Engineering at Virginia Tech, USA, in 1988 and 1990, respectively. He joined Lincoln University, Christchurch, New Zealand in 1990 as a lecturer and was appointed to a personal Chair in 1999 by the university. He founded the Centre for Advanced Computational Solutions (C-fACS) at Lincoln University in 1999. He has been: a Visiting Professor, Integrated Systems Biology Centre/Centre for Mathematical Biology, University of Oxford, UK (Jan - June, 2008, Nov 2010, June 2013), a Visiting Fellow, Princeton University, New Jersey (Jan-June, 2004; July 2006), a Visiting Professor to Institute of Scientific Computing, Technical University of Braunschweig, Germany (since 2001), a Visiting Scholar, Stanford University (Jan-June, 1998), a visiting member of the Centre for Mathematical Biology, Oxford University, a member of Modelling and Simulation Society of Australia and New Zealand and Sigma Xi honour society; and a Panel member of Mathematics, Information Science and Technology (MIST) panel for the PBRF 2012 quality evaluations, Govt of New Zealand.

Gender Dysphoria – A Clinical Assessment

Dr. Morris Bersin

Consultant Psychiatrist, The Evandale Practice, Australia

Email: mbersin0@gmail.com

Abstract:

Gender is as old as Humanity. Gender dysphoria also reaches into antiquity, BUT in today's world has a very different presentation and implications. This presentation will explain the varying definitions related to gender, and the current epidemiology. It will explain an approach to assessment and the basic details of the assessment, which is then related to a series of co-morbidities, such as Body Dysmorphic Disorder, Autistic Spectrum Disorder and other conditions which may complicate the assessment and management. Family supports or resistance is very important at all ages but is progressively more important, the younger the age of the index person. Methodology involved in assessing and dealing with family is discussed. Working in an Integrated Care team with a Psychiatrist, Psychologist, Sexual Health Physician, Endocrinologists, Surgeons and all the General Practitioners, --produces the best results, especially in Private Practice, and this will be explained in detail. Issues relating to age and the law will be mentioned, as will the International Standards of Care from WPATH and the ICD – 11, and their implications.

Biography:

Dr.MORRIS BERSIN – Consultant Psychiatrist M.B.ChB. (Rhod), F.F. Psych (S.A.) FRANZCP. Dr Bersin qualified in 1975 and has been practicing as a consultant psychiatrist since 1994. For the past 11, years Dr Bersin has worked privately at the Evandale Practice located in Bundall on the Gold Coast, Queensland. Dr. Bersin is an adult psychiatrist but also has a special interest in gender assessment and management of young persons, adolescents and adults. Dr Bersin was one of the keynote speakers at the WPATH Conference in Amsterdam, in 2016, on the theme of Gender Incongruence in Children.

The Brain Autistic: Functionality And Executive Functions

Dr. Nora Cavaco

The Nora Cavaco Institute: International Center Of
Neuropsychology & Autism

Email: noracavaco@hotmail.com

Abstract:

A neuropsychological assessment and rehabilitation perspective, enabling us to chart new paths to a greater understanding of functionality and executive functions in autism. The person with the disorder of autism spectrum presents from very early with specific and persistent features in communication and reciprocal social interaction, with restricted and repetitive patterns of behavior, interests and activities which greatly limits and compromises their daily life. The severity of the autistic picture demonstrates differentiated manifestations considering important variables such as the chronological age, the level of development in which it is found which leads to the denomination of spectrum. Since autism is not a degenerative disorder, intervention through learning techniques and methods with strategies of compensation and support must be developed throughout the life provoking gains and significant improvements along the developmental path of the autistic person. Autism is a neurodevelopmental disorder with marked consequences, especially in the maintenance, in the understanding with very visible flaws in the intellectual and functional abilities adaptive. Autism reveals several compromises and difficulties also manifesting bizarre specificities and interests for certain specific situations, such as lights, sounds and what is revealed by the intensity of behavior. It is important to understand autism by identifying the areas involved, the level of their manifestation or severity as well as the whole situation that surrounds them. At the time of the differential diagnosis, we must check whether or not there is a sensory deficit that may compromise the performance of some competence in the referenced and nuclear areas in order to reach the diagnosis of autism. Executive functions in the autistic are compromised, the ability to encode and decode and return verbal or gestural response are not manifested naturally and adjusted. The brain and its areas reveal some behavioral changes that turn out to be behavioral. The sensory organs respond in different ways and with very differentiated levels and extreme variability before certain stimuli such as the intensity of sound, pain, the lights of the odors of the textures, the palate. The stimulation through multisensory techniques and methods contributes greatly to the acquisition in the autistic person of a greater confidence, mastery, knowledge and autonomy in the diverse contexts in its most diverse dimensions and the world in general. Psychological neuro-rehabilitation in autism. After evaluation, neuropsychological rehabilitation seeks through the methods of treatment used, maximize cognitive functions through functionality in the execution of daily tasks and social interaction. Based on a biopsychosocial aspect, psychological rehabilitation involves all those who directly or indirectly intervene with the subject considering the contexts in which it moves, the subjective factors, the family, the peers among others. Based on the neuronal plasticity of the brain's ability to self-regenerate and morphological adaptation, neuropsychological rehabilitation, in relation to some dysfunctions and fragilities in the various developmental areas allows an intervention that aims at recovery, compensation or behavioral substitution

Keywords:

Autism spectrum disorder, neuropsychological assessment, executive functions.

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Biography:

Dr. Nora Cavaco, Psychologist and Hypnotherapist, Portugal, Professor Nora Cavaco has two BSc's degrees, one in Childhood Education and a second one in Educational Psychology and Rehabilitation. Professor Cavaco has also a Master in Educational Practices and in Educational Psychology in the Specialty of Special Educational Needs. All of these four degrees were awarded by the University of Algarve. Moreover, Prof. Nora Cavaco holds a post-graduation degree in Neuropsychology and Dementias by the University of Barcelona and a second post-graduation degree in Neuroscience Applied to Education by FASP University, Faculty of Social Services in Sao Paulo, Brazil. Currently, she is a member of SICA International Research Group at University of Huelva.

Ameliorating Oxaliplatin-Induced Peripheral Sensory Neuropathy Using Metformin in Colorectal Cancer Patients

Prof. Osama Mohamed Ibrahim¹, Basma Mahrous El-fatatry², Fatma Zakaria Hussien³, Tarek Mohamed Mostafa⁴

Clinical Pharmacy Dept., College of Pharmacy, Tanta University, Tanta, Egypt

Email: osamamhi@hotmail.com

Abstract:

Statement of the Problem: Oxaliplatin is an essential drug in treatment of colorectal cancer. Peripheral sensory neuropathy is the most prominently reported adverse effect. No standard agent has been approved for prevention of this neuropathy. **Purpose:** This prospective controlled study was conducted to evaluate the role of in prevention of oxaliplatin-induced peripheral neuropathy. **Methodology & Theoretical Orientation:** From November 2014 to May 2016, 40 patients with colorectal cancer stage III were enrolled and randomly allocated to a control group received 12 cycles of FOLFOX-4 regimen and a metformin group received the same regimen plus metformin 500 mg three times daily. The metformin efficacy was evaluated using the brief pain inventory short form "worst pain" item, National Cancer Institute Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (NCI-CTCAE version 4.0) and a 12-item neurotoxicity questionnaire (Ntx-12) from the validated Functional Assessment of Cancer Therapy/Gynecologic Oncology Group. In addition to malondialdehyde, interleukin-6 and neurotensin serum levels assessment. **Results:** By the end of 12 cycles, the mean pain scores in metformin group were significantly lower than those of control group, (6.7 versus 7.3, $P = 0.005$). Ninety-five percent of patients in control group experienced grade 2 and 3 while 40% of metformin group remained in grade 1 and only 60% experienced grade 2 and 3, $P = 0.002$. Furthermore, metformin group showed significantly higher total scores of Ntx-12 questionnaire than control group (24.0 versus 19.2, $P < 0.001$). Mean serum levels of malondialdehyde and neurotensin were significantly lower in metformin group after 6 and 12 cycles. However, mean serum levels of interleukin-6 showed non-significant difference between the two groups. **Conclusion & Significance:** Our findings may suggest that metformin is a promising drug in protecting colorectal cancer patients against chronic oxaliplatin-induced peripheral sensory neuropathy.

Bioraphy :

Prof. Dr. OSAMA M. IBRAHIM, Clinical Pharmacy Dept., College of Pharmacy, Tanta University, Tanta, Egypt. I got his Master Degree & Ph.D. Degrees in Clinical Pharmacy from the University of the Pacific, School of Pharmacy, Stockton, California, U.S.A. I was the first faculty staff to hold a Ph.D. degree in Clinical Pharmacy in Egypt. I worked as clinical pharmacy professor in addition to a cardiovascular consultant in Riyadh & Jeddah, KSA. I Established Clinical Pharmacy Diploma as well as a PHARM. D. Program in Egypt. My research interest is in the area of Cardiovascular Disorders, Applied Pharmacokinetics, and Drug Information, and Clinical Trials & research

Systems Psyche The Interface between Matter and Consciousness

Dr. A. K. Mukhopadhyay

Professor of Pathology, North DMC Medical College and Hindu Rao Hospital, India
Formerly, Head, Laboratory Medicine, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, India

Email: mukhoak1953@gmail.com

Abstract:

Time is ripe for the Psychology to become truly interdisciplinary and to be identified as a spoke in the wheel of Systems Science. Keeping this goal in view, this workshop in its first phase is intended to (i) elaborate on the Structural constituents of the Psyche namely, Information, Mind, Self, Life and Consciousness (ii) Specify operations of each of its constituents and their interconnectedness as systems (iii) Describe the hierarchically structured labyrinthine decision-making cognitive apparatus and placing it in the context of five nests of nature-consciousness. We will observe pyramidal hierarchy, tangle hierarchy and labyrinthine hierarchy.

In the second phase of the workshop, there would be elaboration on (i) the Ladder of Cognition

(ii) the Canvas of Cognition

- (iii) Relationship between Artificial Intelligence, Natural Intelligence and Human Intelligence and finally,
- (iv) the Layers between neural signaling inside the brain and Consciousness.

In the concluding part of the workshop, the doable research areas connecting psychology with the molecular cell biology

will be discussed to stimulate the young scholars to initiate research works on the topics of

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Adopting laughter therapy to get dosage of happy hormones to remove stress caused by being in slight pain, being depressed, being unhappy anxious or sad. Saying positive affirmations aloud changes body cell

Ms. Suchi Deshpande

Motivational speaker ~ASPIRES SOCIETY, U.K

Email: suchi11sg@gmail.com

Abstract:

Statement of the Problem: There is a lack of awareness about what happy hormones are, how to use positive words to feel energetic and what can be done to get happy hormones. People tend to feel unhappy for multiple reasons and neuropathic pain adds on Stress levels of not only the patient but the caregivers as well. Being in pain leads to feeling depressed and anxious in some cases.

Methodology & Theoretical Orientation: Review of Books and Research shows that getting a dosage of happy hormones will not only ease slight pain of the patient but feeling happy will also have a positive impact on the recovery of the patient. Adopting Laughter therapy and getting hormones which makes one feel good will help many to recover from Neuropathic pain/Long term sadness caused by having grief ,Anger or Resentment, Depression & Anxiety.

Findings: One needs to work on his/her energies using Laughter Therapy which is a positive approach for not having Depression & Anxiety caused by Neuropathic pain. The therapy can be used as a Holistic way to recovery.

Conclusion & Significance: The Laughter therapy which includes ways to get the dosage of happy hormones promotes overcoming Depression & Anxiety caused by Neuropathic pain, is a fun way to manage pain. Repeated sessions to be conducted to remind patients that life while having pain or during the recovery should go beyond just seeking medical and counselling help and also include rebuilding Spiritual, Physical, Emotional, Relational and Mental health. The model has been put together from for testing in many settings including hospitals, elderly homes and senior citizen centres. This is not a research book or paper. It is just an effort to demystify the help available for Depression & Anxiety caused by pain. It is an attempt to motivate and encourage people to seek help and take a simple approach to remember and work on all aspects of their recovery.

Biography :

MS. SUCHI is an experienced International Pre School Principal/Manager who picked up Laughter exercises from many coaches around the world. She then designed 'Laughter Therapy' which is being used in many places such as hospitals and Senior Activity Centres. She provides individual and group therapy in educational and home settings.